

Infinite Loops of Positive Integers Excluding 1, 2, and 4 Exist Within the Collatz Operations

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Abstract

This proof shows that there are infinite loops of positive integers, other than the 4, 2, 1 loop that occurs for all tested positive integers, that exist within the operations presented by the Collatz Conjecture. Proving that another loop exists would disprove the conjecture, as it states that all positive integers shall eventually fall into the 4, 2, 1 loop. This proof uses the Probabilistic method [3]. Moreover, this proof relies on the theorem that there is a chance that a fraction can approximate an irrational number to an arbitrary amount of digits [1]. This paper uses both to state Theorem 1, $\exists(x) \in \mathbb{Z}^+ : x \neq (1, 2, 4), \exists(n, m) \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \exists(c) \in \mathbb{Q}^+ : x = x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$ is true for the specific generation method of x and c , which in turn proves that a loop that does not contain 1, 2, or 4 exists.

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1 Introduction

The Collatz Conjecture prescribes the following procedures on any non-zero, natural number: If a number is even, it is to be halved; if a number is odd, it is to be tripled and subsequently increased by one. The Collatz Conjecture states that all chosen positive integers shall eventually fall into the following loop: 4, 2, 1, 4... This specific loop has been observed for all chosen positive integers [2].

1.1 Previous Attempts

The most recent major contribution to the Collatz Conjecture was performed by Terence Tao. The conclusion drawn from Tao's article [4] is a simple one; that almost all chosen non-zero, natural numbers become less than their starting value. If a number becomes less than its starting value, we can assume it falls into the 4, 2, 1 loop. The proof outlined below states that there is an exceptionally small chance that a loop can form, without containing 1, 2, or 4. These proofs are not mutually exclusive, in fact, Tao's proof creates a void that the following proof will fill.

1.2 Vocabulary

The "Collatz operations" are the repetition of the operations presented by the Collatz Conjecture ad infinitum. This means that any starting integer on which the Collatz operations are performed will end up in a loop of some kind.

A "step" is one singular operation on an integer. This is to say either $3x + 1$ or $\frac{x}{2}$, assuming x is the integer we are operating on.

A "cycle" is a combination of 2 steps; $3x + 1$ and $\frac{x}{2}$. This combination is important because after we perform our first step, we know our new number will be even, so we can confirm what the next step will be $\frac{x}{2}$

A "trajectory" is all the steps and the order they take place for any chosen integer when the Collatz operations are performed on it.

2 Proof that Infinite Loops of Positive Integers that do not Contain 1, 2, and 4 Exist Within the Collatz Operations

To start, we can equate the trajectory of any given integer to a multiplication of the starting integer by a fraction, plus a constant: $x\frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$, where x is the original, natural, and non-zero number, n is the number of times x was multiplied by 3, m

is the number of times x was divided by 2, and c is the accumulation of the added 1 over the whole sequence. According to the rules of the Collatz operations, $x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$ is always an integer. This fact is important and indicates to us that replicating the natural number that we started with is possible, and not infinitely rare.

For example, let us choose 12 as our starting integer, x , pursue its trajectory, and then describe it as $x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$. The trajectory of 12 is as follows; 12, 6, 3, 10, 5, 16, 8, 4, 2, 1. As soon as it reaches 1, we can assume the series 4, 2, 1 loops indefinitely. If we describe the trajectory of 12 as $x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$ once it reaches 16, we obtain the equation $16 = 12 \frac{3^2}{2^3} + \frac{5}{2}$, where n is 2, m is 3 and c is $\frac{5}{2}$ (calculation of c shown by Formula 2, 2.2 is only valid because 12 is generated using Formula 1, 2.1). The following simplification shows this representation functioning correctly.

$$16 = 12 \frac{3^2}{2^3} + \frac{5}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$16 = 12 \frac{9}{8} + \frac{5}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$16 = \frac{27}{2} + \frac{5}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$16 = 16 \quad (4)$$

To continue, for a loop to occur, x must be equal to $x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$. For the aforementioned equality to be true, and since c is always a positive, non-zero number (Formula 2, 2.2), $x \frac{3^n}{2^m}$ must be less than x . Therefore, x must have a coefficient less than 1. In result, $\frac{3^n}{2^m}$ must be less than 1. Because we know that $\frac{3^n}{2^m}$ must be less than 1, we can also assert, by using the Formula 1 (2.1) and 2 (2.2), once n and m are big enough, c is relatively small compared to x . This shows that $\frac{3^n}{2^m}$ must be less than 1, but is instead very close to it. This is true because both are exponential functions, but the function that defines x has a far greater exponent and base, meaning it will increase much faster than c . If we extend this to infinity, the coefficient of x will become effectively 1, and relatively, c will become so small it becomes irrelevant. Therefore, we can investigate the coefficient by using a value of 1 as a maximum value:

$$\frac{3^n}{2^m} = 1 \quad (5)$$

$$3^n = 2^m \quad (6)$$

$$\log(3^n) = \log(2^m) \quad (7)$$

$$n \log(3) = m \log(2) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{n}{m} = \frac{\log(2)}{\log(3)} = \log_3(2) \quad (9)$$

For $x \frac{3^n}{2^m}$ to equal 1, $\frac{n}{m}$ must equal $\log_3(2)$, and because $\log_3(2)$ is an irrational number, we know that using ratios, we can only approximate it. This is useful to the proof because we need a ratio that is slightly under 1. To formulate an accurate approximation, we need n and m to be very large. This is why relative to x , c is small, as stated before.

We can now assume that if we take all possible positive integers for n and m , the possible approximations of $\log_3(2)$ become infinitely accurate. Even though n and m get larger, and c becomes relatively smaller, the possible approximations of $\log_3(2)$ become more precise, eventually becoming infinitely precise, because of the infinite approximation of fractions [1]. This means that, relatively speaking, the value of c is irrelevant. All that is important is that it is positive and non-zero, and that once you add c and $x \frac{3^n}{2^m}$, the sum will always be a positive integer (Formula 2, 2.2). Knowing that, if we take all possible positive integers for m and n , we can assert that there is a non-zero chance that $x = x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$. This means if we consider all positive integers for n and m , there are an infinite amount of positive integer values for m and n that satisfy the following equation; $x = x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$.

Theorem 1 *Let x be generated in accordance to Formula 1 (2.1) and not be equal to 1, 2, or 4. Let c be generated in accordance to Formula 2 (2.2). Let m and n be any positive integer:*

$$\exists(x) \in \mathbb{Z}^+ : x \neq (1, 2, 4), \exists(n, m) \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \exists(c) \in \mathbb{Q}^+ : x = x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c \quad (10)$$

This equation represents infinitely many trajectories that repeat upon themselves. Any trajectory with that property is a loop of numbers within the Collatz operations that does not contain 1, 2, or 4. Confirming their existence disproves the Collatz Conjecture.

2.1 Formula 1, Calculation of x , a Positive Integer That Will Obey Any Set Trajectory Described as $(x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c)$

First of all, we must take note that 2^u has u factors of 2 in its prime factorization. Secondly, in the case of the Collatz Conjecture, $2^u - 1$ will give us a number that is odd and will remain odd (remember that a cycle is: $3x + 1$ followed by $\frac{x}{2}$, this is because, after each $3x + 1$, the number now must be even), until $u - 1$ cycles

have been performed, as shown in Proof 1 (2.3) below. For example, if we define u as 4, we get the number 15, let us now cycle it 4 times; 23, 35, 53, 80. The last term that is odd is the $u - 1$ term.

Most importantly, the formula $(2^n - 1)(2^{((m-n)+1)})$ gives us an x that will obey a trajectory that can be represented as $x \frac{3^n}{2^m}$. This is because we know that $2^{(m-n)+1}$ will be divided immediately because it is a power of 2 until it reaches 1. Then, $2^n - 1$ is odd and will increase according to Proof 1 (2.3). Furthermore, this formula guarantees that the given positive integer will have all extra divisions by 2 happen at the start, and all multiplications by 3 and subsequent divisions 2 happen after all starting divisions by 2. This is crucial to take note of as it confirms the correctness of the following formula and will make c as large as possible.

2.2 Formula 2, Calculation of c of a Positive Integer of the Value $((2^n - 1)(2^{((m-n)+1)}))$

c begins at $\frac{1}{2}$. Repeat $n - 2$ times: $c = \frac{3c+1}{2}$. Repeat 1 time: $c = 3c + 1$. You must repeat the first step $n - 2$ times, and the second step 1 time, because the first cycle is generalized as c starting at $\frac{1}{2}$. Secondly, because $2^n - 1$ is guaranteed to be odd during and after $n - 1$ cycles (Proof 1, 2.3), and one cycle is already consumed by the starting condition of c , we must repeat this step $n - 2$ times. Lastly, because we know that now our number is odd, we must add the last multiplication of 3, without the division. Another effect of Formula 1 (2.1) is that c is as large as it can possibly be. This is essential because it means that our approximations of numbers just under 1 in the fraction $\frac{3^n}{2^m}$ can be as broad as possible. In theory, the actual value of c will never matter, the only two things that are important are that c will always be a positive, non-zero, rational number, and that, according to the definition of the Collatz operations, $x \frac{3^n}{2^m} + c$ is always a positive integer.

2.3 Proof 1, Proof That $(2u - 1)$ Will be Odd After $(u - 1)$ Cycles

If you multiply $2^u - 1$ by 3 and then add 1, and then divide that positive integer by 2, $2^u - 1$, will always be composed of greater powers of 2 than 2^{u-2} once $2^{u-1} - 1$ is removed (unless $2^{u-1} = 1$). This is true because for any u , after the first cycle, the positive integer will be equal to $2^u + 2^{u-1} - 1$. This is because when you perform the cycle on it, you effectively multiply the positive integer by $\frac{3}{2}$ and then add $\frac{1}{2}$. This is equivalent to $(\frac{3}{2}(2^u) - \frac{3}{2}(1)) + \frac{1}{2}$. Once we fully simplify this expression, the result is $2^u + 2^{u-1} - 1$.

$$\left(\frac{3}{2}(2^u) - \frac{3}{2}(1)\right) + \frac{1}{2} \tag{11}$$

$$\left(\frac{2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)(2^u) - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (12)$$

$$\left(\left(\frac{2}{2}(2^u) + \frac{1}{2}(2^u)\right) - \frac{3}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \quad (13)$$

$$\left((2^u) + (2^{u-1}) - \frac{3}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \quad (14)$$

$$2^u + 2^{u-1} - 1 \quad (15)$$

Now that we have simplified our expression, we can consider this expression as having 2 parts: 2^u and $2^{u-1} - 1$. Since 2^u will always be even, and $2^{u-1} - 1$ is always odd, then once we add them, $2^u + 2^{u-1} - 1$, the result must be odd. Now, we can separate the number and only consider $2^{u-1} - 1$, because it will be the smallest number added that is describable as a power of 2 minus a constant. This is the most important part of this proof, as it means we can repeat the proof on this part, as it is a power of 2 minus 1. The cycle can be repeated over and over again, and every time we repeat it we know it will be odd. This capability to be repeated continues until $2^{u-1} - 1$ equals 1, because the result after a cycle must be even $1 * 3 + 1 = 4, \frac{4}{2} = 2$. This proves that $2^u - 1$ is guaranteed to be odd during $u - 1$ cycles, and on the u cycle is even.

References

- [1] James Maynard Dimitris Koukoulopoulos. *ON THE DUFFIN-SCHAEFFER CONJECTURE*. URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1907.04593.pdf>. (accessed: 31.10.2023).
- [2] Patrick Honner. *The Simple Math Problem We Still Can't Solve*. URL: <https://www.quantamagazine.org/why-mathematicians-still-cant-solve-the-collatz-conjecture-20200922/>. (accessed: 31.10.2023).
- [3] Jan Vondrák Jiří Matoušek. *The Probabilistic Method*. URL: <https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~15850/handouts/matousek-vondrak-prob-ln.pdf>. (accessed: 31.10.2023).
- [4] Terence Tao. *ALMOST ALL ORBITS OF THE COLLATZ MAP ATTAIN ALMOST BOUNDED VALUES*. URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1909.03562.pdf>. (accessed: 30.10.2023).